

**Cross-cutting activity 1:
Support to the generation and
the development of start-ups
and spin-offs**

— Fundraising activities

**Leader:
UNITS**

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1. INTRODUCTION

The present document reports on the activities carried out and results achieved by Alpimerchant S.r.l. on behalf of the University of Trieste, as part of the fundraising phase of the CCI initiative. The report was produced by Alpimerchant S.r.l..

Through the Cross-cutting Activity 1, the iNEST project aims to transform innovative ideas into concrete projects and business ventures capable of generating a significant impact on the innovation ecosystem in the Northeast. The main objective of this activity is to accompany start-ups in their growth, supporting them in project development and preparation for possible future investments.

This report focuses on the final phase of the activities, with particular reference to the one-to-one consultancy sessions to assess the business potential of the start-ups and the final event in Trieste, during which start-ups and investors had the opportunity to interact and exchange ideas. The qualitative and quantitative analyses presented here aim to provide a clear picture of the results achieved, as well as of the areas for improvement for the start-ups.

2. ONE-ON-ONE CONSULTANCY SESSIONS

The consultancy sessions were organized as online meetings lasting an average of approximately 90 minutes, with the following agenda:

- Mutual introduction of the meeting participants and of the purpose of the meeting - 20 minutes available to the founder teams to present their start-ups
- Questions and further discussion
- Feedback on the meeting and sharing of contact details for future communication between the parties involved.

2.1. Work structure

In general, the focus was on the six fundamental themes that every innovation project must highlight in order to attract the interest of an investor:

1. **TEAM:** are there the necessary motivations and skills (technical, commercial, organizational-business) for the development of the project? Is there a willingness to fully dedicate oneself to the project? Is there the necessary leadership ability?
2. **MARKET:** is it large enough? Have the customer and their needs been clearly identified?
3. **TIMING:** is the market ready to embrace the idea?
4. **COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE:** are there barriers to entry? Have competitors been analyzed? Are there characteristics that distinguish the offer from competitors that can be maintained over time?

5. **SCALABILITY:** how much can the value grow over time and how quickly?
6. **EXIT:** what exit opportunities are there for investors?

The main objective of these interviews was to provide targeted feedback (with particular reference to the six points above), which would be useful to start-ups in preparing for future meetings with external investors.

The consultancy team used an evaluation grid (see table below) to rank the initiatives analyzed, with the highest scores corresponding to initiatives that were better organized overall for dialogue with potential investors.

Each of the start-ups involved in the one-on-one sessions received individual feedback from the consultants.

Evaluation grid employed:

Category	Factors assessed	
Preliminary conditions	1	Market size / growth rate
	2	Product development stage consistent with project lifecycle stage
	3	Round characteristics
	4	Post-round cap table overview
Quality of the entrepreneurial team	1	Quality of the founding team
	2	Determination and dedication to the business project
Market conditions	1	Market activity in terms of M&A transactions
	2	Competition rate (n. of startups in the market / innovation rate)
Product/Service & Business Model	1	Product/service innovativeness & business model
	2	Product impact
	3	Competitive advantage
Results achieved	1	Traction achieved so far in relation to available resources
	2	"Degree of validation" (problem, solution, market)
	3	Identification of the key driver of the growth plan

2.2. Emerging qualitative aspects

Unfortunately, some start-up initiatives withdrew from the iNEST CCI project or were not available for the consultancy session (the dropout rate was higher for initiatives in the first cycle, as they had completed the previous phases of the acceleration program earlier).

In general, it is clear that teams find it difficult to transform a good (business) idea into a business venture, which is a necessary condition for attracting the interest of investors. In some cases, it was clear that the teams, although they had made an interesting effort to explore the validity of the original idea, had not yet developed a real entrepreneurial conviction.

Some of the initiatives analyzed were still too “immature” with teams that were not sufficiently structured. Although they showed interesting potential, not all of them were ready to interact with external investors in the short term. The areas they will need to work on most include defining their value proposition and commercial strategy and consolidating their teams.

About ten initiatives were found to be adequately structured, and we believe they are already in a position to hold preliminary discussions with venture capital operators.

2.3. Quantitative aspects

Total number of start-ups to be analyzed: 30.

Number of meetings organized: 20 (a further 4 start-ups were contacted by telephone but were not available for a meeting).

The 5 start-ups that received the highest ratings are: BBSof, SIPEOM - Probabilistic Emissions Forecast, Discovera, Algae Scope, Robotizr.

3. VENTURE DAY (event in Trieste)

The “Venture Day” session took place in Trieste on the 18th of September 2025 and represented a key moment of discussion and visibility for start-ups, while also allowing valuable information to be gathered on market interests. The session was attended by five institutional investors with complementary profiles, representing different segments of the Italian innovation ecosystem. The presence of players with different experiences and interests contributed to creating a varied discussion, offering start-ups the opportunity to test their proposals in front of interlocutors with different perspectives, from institutional investors to corporations, to business angel networks.

The consultants supported the organization in identifying and engaging investors attending the event:

IAG (Italian Angels for Growth), one of Italy's leading business angel networks, takes an early-stage investment approach based on broad sector expertise and strong mentorship capabilities for entrepreneurial teams. Ticket size 100k-1M €.

Vesper Holding, a venture capital firm founded by the Mondini family, brings together around fifty shareholders and invests in early-stage Italian start-ups, with tickets ranging from 50k to 100k €. It

focuses on innovative projects with high potential, leveraging the network of skills and relationships of its partners.

Growth Capital, an advisory firm specialized in extraordinary finance transactions for start-ups and scale-ups, combines financial expertise with a focus on emerging market opportunities.

ZNext (Zanichelli Venture), a corporate vehicle of the Zanichelli publishing group, active in supporting innovative projects in the field of education and digital learning, with a strategic focus on open innovation.

Obloo Ventures, a venture capital fund that invests in high-tech startups, with a particular focus on deep tech and digital projects. It concentrates on scouting, evaluation, execution, and exit, supporting tech startups from the conception phase to full operation and exit.

The following startup teams were present at the event: SIPEOM - Probabilistic Emissions Forecast, Discovera, Algae Scope, Robotizr, AIRFARM, EcoBot, CyNexoSrl (SniffNano), Fenix Ceramics, Bioxygen.

To facilitate communication between start-ups and investors and to facilitate contacts and mutual understanding between the parties involved, the start-ups were asked to upload the following to a shared area: the project pitch and a one pager presentation containing the most significant information about the project (Business description; Product/Service (indicating the TRL); Market and Competition; Business Model; Team; Results achieved; Key next steps; Capital to be raised; Use of funds to be raised; Revenue and Cost Estimates for the coming years; Exit strategy; Expectation from the meeting with investors). The investment players were asked to provide a short bio.

During the morning, the top five startups on the list presented their pitches (10-minute presentation + 10-minute Q&A) to the audience and VC operators in attendance. During the afternoon, physical spaces were set up for 30-minute individual meetings where startups could hold private meetings with the investors present. There were 16 formal meetings (not including informal meetings that took place throughout the day).

Interactions with investors showed general curiosity and gave startups a first opportunity to engage directly with different investment operators. At this time, it is not yet possible to predict which startups will receive expressions of interest or requests for further information. However, the team of consultants has made itself available to be contacted by startups in the future to discuss the outcomes of the meetings and to offer advice on how to organize the next steps.

4. FURTHER INVESTOR CONTACT DEVELOPMENT

In parallel with the Trieste session, work began on establishing and consolidating contacts with additional investors, with the aim of maintaining interest and promoting future opportunities for discussion. This process does not focus exclusively on the most advanced startups, but also involves seven or eight other companies that have shown interesting potential in terms of innovation and market prospects.

The consultants' network allows to contact a significant number of startup investment operators in Italy. Starting with the event in Trieste, the most promising startups will be provided with 2-3 contacts with Business Angels / VCs whose investment philosophies most closely match the characteristics of

the startups. It is therefore likely that startups will receive different contacts depending on their sector (e.g. deep tech, digital, life sciences, etc.) and their stage of development.

This activity does not yet guarantee formal meetings, but it represents an important strategic step in ensuring that startups gradually begin to appear on the radar of the investor ecosystem. From this perspective, preliminary contact with selected investors increases the visibility of the companies involved and lays the foundations for potential collaboration or investment opportunities in the medium term. The consultancy team will carefully assess whether and how to promote meetings with VCs to avoid the risk that rushing things could preclude subsequent meetings with startups that may inevitably prove to be more “mature.”

We are confident that the suggestions shared with the teams during the one-on-one consulting phase and the creation of one-pager presentation sheets for individual projects, which can be used in different contexts, will provide useful funding opportunities for startups.

However, we will have to wait a few months to understand what the feedback from investors will be and the real possibilities for fundraising by the projects.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The final phase of the iNEST project allowed us to complete the fundraising support process and provide start-ups with concrete feedback to prepare them for future interactions with investors.

The consulting activity confirms the importance of structured and targeted support for new initiatives to accompany them into the world of investors and suggests continuing to develop preparation and follow-up tools to maximize the effectiveness of matching with investors.